

REPRESENTATION OF THE FUTURE TENSE IN THE LINGUISTIC IMAGE OF THE UZBEK AND ENGLISH WORLDS.

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Abstract. This article covers the expression of the future tense in the linguistic image of the Uzbek and English worlds. Also, the differences in the meanings of the grammatical tense category in the world linguistic image of the languages being compared are highlighted with the help of examples.

Keywords: world, linguistic image, future tense, action, Uzbek language, English language, grammatical form, category.

According to M. Iriskulov, the future tense indicates that the action will take place after the speech process. The expression and types of meaning of this tense are also not the same in languages. In modern English, this meaning is expressed in this way:

1. Through the auxiliary verbs *shall*, *will* and, *the infinitive*. The auxiliary verb *shall* is used for the first person singular and plural and *will* is used for the second and third persons. For example:

I shall read it later (Men buni keyinroq o'qiyman).

He will phone you up (U senga qo'ng'iroq qiladi).

This method expresses the simple future tense.

2. The meaning of the future tense can be expressed from the perspective of the past tense.

3. The meaning of another action that takes place before the action that will take place in the future tense can be expressed. This is expressed as a result of combining the infinitive with the two auxiliary verbs *should* and *would* from the future tense: *John said that he would come. Jon kelishini aytdi.* The auxiliary verb *should* is used for the first person, and *would* for the second person. The third tense of the future tense is a verb with two future tenses, one of which will happen before the other or two actions that will happen in succession, for example: *When you come he will have finished his composition (Sen kelganingda, u inshoni yozib bo'lgan bo'ladi).* A. Sodikov confirms the same meaning of the future tense.

The future tense in Uzbek is very different from that in other languages. The Uzbek language has no verb form that means the exact future tense. As mentioned above, one form of the verb also means the future tense. Both future tenses consist of the future tense verb and the future tense verb.

The future tense verb conjecture expresses that the action is expected to happen after the speech. This meaning is expressed by marking the adjective formed with the affixal morpheme - (a)r: *Men ishlarman – Biz ishlarmiz.*

The purpose of the verb in the future tense means an action that is intended to be performed after the speech process. This meaning is expressed by adding and accenting the affixal morpheme *-moqchi* to the verb stem, or by adding and accenting the affixal morpheme *-digan* to the present participle. *Men ishlamoqchiman - Biz ishlamoqchimiz. work.*

It is clear from this that in Uzbek language, the future tense and target verbs are different. These differences are represented by grammatical forms.

According to M. Iriskulov, the future tense in Uzbek does not correspond to any of the known Indo-European languages. Therefore, each language has its types of grammatical meanings and ways of expressing them.

In English, the following forms of the verb are distinguished:

1. The Simple Future Tense is made from the auxiliary verbs *shall* (first person singular and plural) and *will* (second and third persons singular and plural) and the infinitive form of the main verb without "to" is used. In modern English, it has become common to use the auxiliary verb *will* in all persons, both singular and plural. *I shall (will) do it tomorrow // Men buni ertaga bajaraman.* In oral speech, abbreviated forms of auxiliary verbs are used in affirmative and interrogative sentences.

Simple Future expresses actions that will happen in the future. The following tenses are often used in the future tense: *tonight (bugun tunda), tomorrow (ertaga), the day after tomorrow (indinga), in two days (ikki kundun keyin), next week (kelasi hafta(da), next month (kelasi oy(da), soon (yaqinda, tezda).* For example: *She travels a lot (U juda ko'p sayohat qiladi). Tomorrow she will be in Rome, next week she'll be in Tokio (Bugun u Londonda. Ertaga u Rimda bo'ladi, kelasi hafta(da) Tokioda bo'ladi).*

The Future Continuous Tense is used in the following cases:

1. When expressing actions that will happen in the near or far future: *What will you be doing tomorrow? (Ertaga nima qilasan?).*

2. When expressing an action that will happen at a certain time in the future: *I shall be doing my homework at eight o'clock tomorrow again (Men ertaga soat sakkizda yana uy vazifamni tayyorlayotgan bo'laman).*

The Future Perfect Tense is formed by the auxiliary verbs *shall have* or *will have* and the past participle of the main verb. The Future Perfect tense expresses another action that will take place before an action that will happen in the future. In this sense, the words that come with the preposition *by*, for example, *by the end of the year (yil oxiriga kelib), at that time (o'sha vaqtda), by tomorrow (ertaga), by this afternoon (bugun kunduzi), by tonight (bugun tunda/oqshom), by next week/month/year (kelasi hafta/oy/yil) comes.*

English verbs expressed in this tense are usually translated into Uzbek using the past participle (-gan) or adverb (-ib) and various auxiliary verbs (for example, *tugatgan bo'ladi* or *tugatib bo'lgan bo'ladi; ko'rib chiqadi yoki ko'rib chiqqan bo'ladi*). For example: *By the end of the winter season, more tourists will have visited the island than ever before (Qish mavsumining oxiriga kelib orolga har doimgidan ham ko'proq sayyohlar kelib ketishgan bo'ladi).* *I left several letters unfinished on my desk, but I will have finished them before noon tomorrow (Yozuv stolimda bir nechta tugatilmagan xatlarni qoldirdim, lekin ertaga peshingacha ularni tugatib bo'laman).*

It seems that even in English, future tense verbs express different actions in meaning, the action can be definite, indefinite, continuing, or beginning in the past and ending in the future. In the table below, we try to reflect the specific aspects and common features of the future tense in the linguistic picture of the Uzbek and English language world.

	English language	Uzbek language
Past tense	Simple past tense (Past simple)	Yaqin o'tgan zamon
	The future continuous tense of the past tense.	Uzoq o'tgan zamon
	Past continuous form	O'tgan zamon hikoya fe'li
		O'tgan zamon davom fe'li
Present tense	Simple Present Tense	Aniq hozirgi zamon

	present continuous tense (Continuous)	hozirgi zamon davom fe'li
	present perfect tense (Present Perfect Tense)	hozirgi-kelasi zamon fe'li
Future tense	The Simple Future Tense	kelasi zamon kelasi zamon gumon fe'li
	The Future Continuous Tense	kelasi zamon maqsad fe'li
	The Future Perfect Tense	

In this table, we have highlighted the tense category and its meanings in English and Uzbek with different colours. It seems that the classification of the meaning of each tense in these languages is quantitatively and substantively different. There are 3 forms of past tense in English and 4 forms in Uzbek. It is important to distinguish between them not by the meaning of the action relating to time, but by the characteristics such as the duration of the occurrence. Although present tense verbs are divided into 3 groups in English and Uzbek, they are reflected differently in the linguistic picture of these languages: in English, simple, continuous, and resultative present tenses are distinguished, while in Uzbek, present definite, present continuous, and present future still are distinguished. differs. This point can also be made about future tense meanings. It seems that the specific meanings of the grammatical tense category differ in the world linguistic landscape of the languages being compared. It should be noted that the Uzbek language has rich possibilities due to the diverse meaning of the tense category.

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